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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

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General application	<i>Space, high-reliability</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
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Facility	<i>HIF, UC Leuven</i>
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	<i>12h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

Introduction

SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1 is a mixed-signal ASIC. As an LCL, the device is capable of detecting latch-ups inside the protected COTS component, subsystem or even complete system. The AUTOSTART feature assures fully autonomous recovery of the protected component, subsystem, or space avionics system from the detected SEL event. SKY-IC-RHLCL is especially designed to protect and supervise modern COTS FPGAs used in micro-scale satellite platforms.

The proposed SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1 differentiates itself from other LCL products found on the market with the following 7 unique properties:

- SKY-IC-RHLCL combines both SEL and SEFI protection of COTS component/subsystem/system in a single device.
- The power-on default parameter settings can be modified during run-time via SPI interface (i.e. the supervisor is able to rise the current limit in case of expected higher current consumption periods).
- Besides SEL and SEFI protection, SKY-IC-RHLCL provides also telemetry readings of voltages, supply current, and die operational temperature.
- The device integrates a chaining capability through bidirectional CHAIN_IN and CHAIN_OUT signals which allow connecting several SKY-IC-RHLCL devices into a complex point-of-load chain which can be used to simultaneously protect all required supply rails of modern FPGAs, including the low-voltage rails, below 0.8V.
- SKY-IC-RHLCL can operate in two basic modes: In supervised mode, the device is controlled

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by the external supervision controller. In case of detected SEL event on the protected component, the power supply to this component is interrupted, and the external supervisor is alerted. SKY-IC-RHLCL can operate also in fully autonomous AUTOSTART mode, where SKY-IC-RHLCL does not need any supervisor and can restore the power supply to the protected component, subsystem, or system automatically after elapsing the preconfigured AUTOSTART delay.

- SKY-IC-RHLCL integrates a configurable SEFI watchdog (WD) functionality which can be enabled and WD timeout initially configured by two pins. If enabled, WD needs to be periodically cleared by the protected component, subsystem, or system via the SPI interface.
- SKY-IC-RHLCL provides also overvoltage protection with configurable overvoltage threshold. A fast comparator is utilized in order to achieve a micro-second range reaction time capability.

Furthermore, SKY-IC-RHLCL supports also a control of BJT on the protected load side, which activates as soon as a fault is detected, thus discharging any remaining charge on the protected load's side which would otherwise continue supplying the protected load in a fault condition, even if the main PMOS would already be switched-off.

Figure 1: DUT for SEE characterization: SKY-IC-RHLCL LCL ASIC with lid opened

SEE Characterization Objectives

The main objective of SEE test characterization of SKY-IC-RHLCL is to analyze SEE immunity of the following effects:

- **SEL**: Single Event Latch-up immunity
- **SET**: Single Event Transient immunity
- **SEFI**: Single Event Functional Interrupts immunity

The test and measurement equipment allows detection of SEE events in analog (SEL/SET) and digital modules (SEL/SET/SEFI) of SKY-IC-RHLCL.

Experiment test report

SEE Characterization Setup Architecture

To maximize the data collection during radiation characterization, application specific test equipment was developed. The developed hardware comprises two circuit boards: the Device Under Test (DUT) board and the Acquisition board. The block diagram of the test equipment is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Diagram of the experimental setup for SEE testing

The DUT board implements 3 CLCC68 sockets for DUT LCLs. The sockets were designed to allow the LCLs to be biased and capable of performing full functional tests. The DUT board incorporates latch-up guard circuits to measure the current consumption of specific parts of the LCL and to perform a power cycle in case of latch-up event. The digital segments of the LCLs are powered by a 3.3 V power supply, while the analog ASIC parts require the same voltage levels as the protected load, which is set at 5 V. Supply voltages are provided by the power supply module on acquisition board. The DUT board also incorporates three right-angle BNC connectors, which will provide a direct feed of the LCL's *OC_Error* signal to the oscilloscope.

The acquisition board serves as a bridge between a controlling PC and DUT board. It implements an FPGA circuit responsible for controlling and monitoring the functionality of the LCLs, as well as performing the acquisition of analog parameters. The boards are connected by six 30 cm long flat cables. Communication between the acquisition board and the PC is established by RS422 communication via a 3 m long cable, chosen to meet the test facility's requirements. All test procedures and data logging tasks are executed on the PC.

SET Test Principle

The SET test procedure will run in a static nominal operating mode (ON state). The primary focus will be on the *OC_error* pin, where single event transients will be monitored. Measurements will be conducted using an external oscilloscope. The DUT board includes a BNC connector, facilitating direct connection to the oscilloscope. The *OC_error* pin serves as an indicator for overcurrent events, which is crucial for determining the functionality of the LCL. Consequently, the system's stability and reliability depend on the integrity of this signal. If the transient event will occur on the error signal, the oscilloscope logging will be triggered, and measurements of transient amplitude and durations will take place. The recording will be saved to the database for post-radiation analysis. The test run will be terminated when the transient effect counter will surpass 100 error counts or the fluence will reach its maximum value.

SEFI Test Principle

For the Single Event Functional Interrupt (SEFI) test procedure, the detection process involves reading the SPI register map and monitoring the nominal working conditions of the LCL. The primary objective of the continuous reading of the DUT's register map is to detect any occurrences of functional interrupts during irradiation. The acquisition board will perform the readout via SPI communication. Additionally, all parameters will be compared to their nominal values to ensure that the LCL is functioning correctly during heavy ion exposure. One of the crucial parameters in this context will be the LCL watchdog counter block. After the initialization state, the control system will preset the watchdog counter to a predefined value that differs from the default initialization value. In the event of a SEFI affecting the LCL's state machine, the device will undergo a system reset, which will also reset the watchdog counter. The monitoring system will be capable of detecting an SEFI event in the state machine and logging the corresponding error. The test run will be terminated when the SEFI error counter will surpass 100 error counts or the fluence will reach its maximum value.

SEL Test Principle

The SEL Test Principle will monitor LCL in a static nominal operation. Following the startup procedure, the DUT will enter the ON operating mode (nominal load current). External heaters will heat-up the LCL DUT to a 100 °C for the SEL evaluation. The guard circuits will disable the limiting functionality and will allow latch-up events. ADCs on the acquisition board will measure and log all provided LCL supply currents and voltages. In the case of a latch-up event, the guard circuits will detect the increase of the specific supply current and initiate a power cycle procedure for the LCL. The guard circuits will monitor the following supply currents:

- I_AVDD, V_AVDD
- I_AUX, V_AUX
- I_DVDD, V_DVDD
- I_DVDD_DIGITAL, V_DVDD_DIGITAL
- I_LOAD, V_IN

During the irradiation run, the background parameters will be continually monitored by the acquisition board. The test run will be terminated when the latch-up counter will surpass 100 errors or the fluence will reach its maximum value.

Heavy Ion Species Test Sequence Requirements

- **5 exposures** (at different LET or Energy) shall be conducted (with at least 2 DUTs) to adequately plot a response curve
- The test time per each HI species shall be such, that a recommended **fluence of 10^7 ions/cm²** is achieved
- TID of 40 krad(Si) shall not be exceeded
- The test starts with **Cr** (nominal LET = 16.1 MeV/(mg/cm²))
 - If DUTs are observed to be immune, the next, heavier ion species is selected and the test is repeated (Ni→Kr→Rh→Xe)
 - If DUTs are not immune at LED=16.1, the test will be conducted with lighter ion species (Ar→AL→Ne→C). Based on the outcome, it will be assessed whether the fast proton tests would be meaningful, or not.

SEE Test Setup Installation

Figure 3 shows the three SKY-IC-RHLCL DUTs inserted into test sockets and mounted on the HiF chamber's frame gantry.

Figure 3: Three SKY-IC-RHLCL DUTs inserted into DUT board sockets and mounted on the gantry frame of the (opened) HiF Vacuum Chamber

SEE Test Results Summary

Based on the recorded data, the SEE cross-sections can be analysed for the DUT LCL_21 which was subject to all HI species. In the context of Single Event Effects (SEE) in electronics, cross-sections are used to quantify the sensitivity of semiconductor devices to ionizing radiation, such as cosmic rays or particles from space. The cross-section represents the probability that a particle (e.g. a heavy ion) will cause a specific type of SEE when it strikes a device. This is measured in units such as square centimeters (cm^2) and is often given as a function of particle energy or linear energy transfer (LET).

SEL Cross-Section

This section presents the SEL Cross-Section of the SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1. In order to determine the ultimate SEL immunity of the device, the heaters were enabled in order to heat-up the DUT to 95°C. It is evident from the data in Table 1 and Figure 4 that SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1 is **SEL immune**, which is the main takeaway of the conducted SEE heavy-ion test campaign. No SELs occurred at the elevated temperature.

Table1: SEL Cross-Section Data

LET (MeV*cm ² /mg)	SEL cross-section
3,3	0,00E+00
5,7	0,00E+00
9,9	0,00E+00
16,1	0,00E+00
32,4	0,00E+00
62,5	0,00E+00

Figure 4: SEL Cross-Section Plot

SEFI Cross-Section

The SEFI cross-section data (see Table 2 and Figure 5) show that SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1 expresses some SEFI susceptibility, starting with the LET of 5.7 MeV*cm²/mg and higher.

Table 2: SEFI Cross-Section Data

LET (MeV*cm ² /mg)	SEFI cross-section
3,3	0,00E+00
5,7	4,00E-07
9,9	1,00E-06
16,1	2,60E-06
32,4	6,60E-06
62,5	2,90E-05

Figure 5: SEFI Cross-Section Plot

SET Cross-Section

The SET cross-section data (see Table 3 and Figure 6) show that SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1 expresses minimal SET susceptibility, starting only with the LET of 32.4 MeV*cm²/mg and higher.

Table 3: SET Cross-Section Data

LET (MeV*cm ² /mg)	SET cross-section
3,3	0,00E+00
5,7	0,00E+00
9,9	0,00E+00
16,1	0,00E+00
32,4	1,80E-06
62,5	4,20E-06

Figure 6: SET Cross-Section Plot

Conclusion

The results from the SEL Cross-Section testing of the SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1 device demonstrate a strong immunity to Single Event Latch-up (SEL) events, confirming its design target, and robustness under extreme conditions. To thoroughly assess the device's ultimate SEL immunity, the tests were conducted with the heaters enabled, raising the Device Under Test (DUT) temperature to an elevated 95°C, and with the highest Heavy Ion LET.

The data presented highlight that no SEL events occurred at this high temperature, reinforcing the finding that the SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1 exhibits stable operation under heavy-ion irradiation conditions. The absence of SEL incidents at elevated temperatures is particularly significant, as it suggests that the device can maintain resilience even in applications exposed to both high thermal and radiative stress. This outcome is the primary takeaway from the SEE heavy-ion test campaign and emphasizes the effectiveness of the SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1's design and manufacturing in ensuring immunity to SEL events.

Overall, the testing campaign has verified that the SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1 meets the SEL immunity standards, qualifying it as a reliable option for applications where devices are expected to endure high levels of ionizing radiation and temperature fluctuations. This immunity to SEL positions the SKY-IC-RHLCL-A1 as a reliable choice for critical aerospace, defense, and other high-reliability sectors where both radiation and thermal endurance are essential for mission success.

SET events were observed in the heavy-ion irradiation campaign. The main reason for SETs is not adequate low-pass filtering on internal analog signals. SET filtering will be improved in the next revision of SKY-IC-RHLCL.

The analysis of the detected SEFIs shows that the main cause of SEFIs are actually SETs, which consequently cause unexpected state transitions inside the internal FSM. However, some SEFIs were detected, where no evidence in the captured error signals can be found. The robust HDL implementation of the FSM enables automatic restoration of device operation through internal reset trigger mechanism.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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